

Synthesis of Sulphones and Related Compounds

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Many sulphones are known to have insecticidal¹⁻³ and acaricidal^{4,5} properties. The allied compound, 1-phenyl-2-phenylsulphonylhydrazine, has been reported as an insecticide³. Recently several non-fluorosulphonylhydrazones⁶⁻⁸ have been prepared and many of them have been found active against a variety of bacteria⁶. The data on their pesticidal activity are, however, lacking in the literature. It was considered therefore worthwhile to synthesise the fluoro analogues of sulphones and sulphonylhydrazones with a view to studying their pesticidal properties. The compounds prepared are recorded in Tables I and II.

TABLE I

Fluorodiarylsulphones.

No.	Ar.	M.P.	%Yield.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
					Found.	Reqd.
1	4-Chlorophenyl	142-43°	51	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₂ ClFS	11.38	11.25
2	4-Fluorophenyl	110°	74	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₂ F ₂ S	11.22	11.04
3	4-Bromophenyl	150-51°	48	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₂ BrFS	9.46	9.73
4	4-Methylphenyl	126-28°	64	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ FS	11.47	12.12
5	1-Naphthyl	174-76°	84	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₂ FS	10.02	10.67
6	4-Fluoronaphthyl	148-50°	84	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ O ₂ F ₂ S	10.39	10.07

General Method of Preparation of Fluorodiaryl Sulphones.—A mixture of appropriate hydrocarbon (0.1*M*), aryl sulphonyl chloride (0.1*M*), and anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.15*M*) in carbon disulphide (80 ml) was refluxed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The solvent was removed and the residue was further heated at 120-50° for 1 hr. After cooling and decomposing with ice-cold hydrochloric acid, the sulphone was isolated in the usual way.

1. Metcalf, "Organic Insecticides", p. 197.
2. U.S.P. 2,645,592/1953.
3. Frear, "Chemistry of Pesticides", pp. 29, 101.
4. *Chem. Abst.*, 1957, 51, 11393.
5. B.P. 792045/1958.
6. Zimmer *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1959, 24, 1667.
7. Cremlyn, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 1329.
8. Munshi *et al.*, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, 1, 311.

Fluoroarylsulphonylhydrazones were prepared according to the method of Zimmer *et al.*⁶. A methanolic solution of the appropriate aldehyde (0.1M) was treated with a methanolic solution of fluoroarylsulphonylhydrazine (0.1M) (obtained by treating appropriate arylsulphonyl chloride (1M) with hydrazine hydrate (2M) in light petroleum] and the mixture was refluxed for 1hr. On pouring into water, concentrating, and cooling, the required sulphonylhydrazone was obtained, which was purified by recrystallisation from aqueous ethanol. Characteristics and analyses of the compounds prepared are reported in Table II.

TABLE II

Fluoroarylsulphonylhydrazones.

No.	Ar'.	M.P.	%Yield.	Formula.	%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.		%Sulphur.	
					Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
Ar ₁ =2-Methyl-5-fluoro-P.										
1	4-Dimethylamino-P	60°	48	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂ FS	56.42	57.31	5.90	5.37	9.14	9.55
2	4-Hydroxy-P	101-102°	20	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₂ FS	54.22	54.54	4.05	4.22	9.84	10.28
3	2-Hydroxy-P	80°	51	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₂ FS	54.68	54.54	3.91	4.22	10.51	10.28
4	4-Methoxy-P	162°	43	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₂ FS	56.42	55.90	5.20	4.65	9.26	9.93
5	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxy-P	148°	46	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₂ FS	52.43	53.25	4.73	4.43	9.01	9.17
6	Styryl	130-32°	46	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ FS	60.64	60.37	4.74	4.72	10.14	10.06
Ar ₁ =4-Fluoro-P.										
7	4-Hydroxy-P	226-28°	24	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₂ FS	52.07	53.06	4.12	3.74	10.72	10.86
8	4-Dimethylamino-P	238-40°	49	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ FS	55.41	56.07	4.60	4.98	9.33	9.97
9	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxy-P	138-39°	45	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₂ FS	52.42	51.85	4.51	4.02	9.61	9.87

N.B. P-denotes phenyl.

The pesticidal activity of these compounds is under investigation and the results will be communicated in due course.

The authors express their grateful thanks to Dr. R. P. Rastogi, Professor and Head of the Department of Chemistry, University of Gorakhpur, for providing necessary facilities and to Dr. K. C. Joshi for his kind interest.